

INFLUENCE OF POWDER COATING PRE-CURING TIME ON INTERFACE COATING/EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

In automotive and aeronautic applications, substrates are coated for protective, functional and/or decorative purposes. Such applications are strongly impacted by recent regulatory constraints (REACH) which aim to eliminate hazardous products, and to limit volatile organic compounds (VOCs)^{1,2,3}. Thus, the manufacturers look for an environmentally way of painting while keeping a high performance level of product. Powder coating is a painting product completely solvent-free. The ability to apply this modern environmentally coating on metal and heat resistance composite was a real advantage for industrial applications.⁴

Over the past years, the use of powder coatings has been increased due to their environmental attributes, economical benefits and performance advantages. Consequently, their consumption on the market has been significantly growing. At the same time, manufacturers are developing wide range of powder coatings that offer high functional performance and overall aesthetic of the applied films³. In wooden and plastic sectors, some problems related to handling process and adhesion results are found. For that, it is normal that the market is going toward the development of products where powder paint cannot currently replace liquid-based paints. Unfortunately, several technological troubles still affect the application process of powder paint, above all, on heat sensitive and electrical insulating substrates.^{3,5}

Powder coatings cannot be air-dried and commonly require quite higher curing temperature (up to 120°C) to establish full film properties. These higher cure temperatures limit the types of substrates on which this technology can be applied. Practically, the deposition of powder coatings is realized by

flowing it to the substrate through a gun, which applies an electrostatic charge for the individual polymer particles. The coated substrate is then heated in a curing oven in order to coalesce the polymer particles and form a continuous film on surface. Here, the nature of the substrate plays a major role in adhesion process of powder coatings. When using a metal substrate, this procedure shows effective results due to the conductive properties of the metallic substrate and its good resistance against deformation at high temperature^{6,7,8}. Powder paints can only be applied on electrically conductive or, at least, semi-conductive or antistatic substrate. This limitation makes the coating process still more troubled on electrical insulating substrates. In this case, surface activation processes like flame spraying, corona and plasma treatments, or the use of electrical solvent-based conductive primer are strictly required before application of powder coating.³

In addition, when the substrate is a polymer based material, some problems related to the adhesion strength and curing temperature can limit the application of powder coatings. Hence, it is necessary to diminish the curing temperature and find an alternative method to coat this type of substrate. Such advances could also translate into energy savings or higher productivities during the industrial painting operations⁹. The technical problems associated with development of low temperature curable powder coatings are several-fold. To be useful, any thermosetting coating must be unreactive at room temperature while possessing sufficient reactivity at the desired cure time/temperature conditions. e.g. the system must be stable at room temperature towards both chemical reaction and physical sintering or agglomeration. In addition, a low temperature curable system must

possess a crosslinker which reacts at low temperature. The polymeric components must melt and flow prior to crosslinking. These requirements make the problem more challenging and the development of entire coating systems, not just new crosslinkers, is required⁹. Briefly, the technological challenge is to provide a powder coating suitable for applying on heat sensitive and electrical insulating substrates, reducing the curing temperature and avoiding any expensive or non-automatic surface activation process.³

It is well known that the adhesion between two materials is highly dependent on the interface which could be associated to an interphase in some cases. Although the concept of the interphase has been widely accepted, there are only a limited number of investigations which provide quantitative characteristics on organic/organic interphase^{10,11}. In this study, our objective is to present an alternative method for powder coating deposition on composite material, and obviously to characterize the organic/organic interface or interphase formed between the powder coatings and the polymer based composite. In order to understand the adhesion mechanisms, the influence of cure time/temperature conditions on interface/interphase characteristics has been investigated. Physical and chemical analyses have been performed to highlight in depth the properties of the adhesive interface/interphase. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Modulated Temperature Differential Scanning Calorimetry (MTDSC) have been used to study the structural and thermal properties. Infrared Spectroscopy has been applied to chemically identify the different components of the interface/interphase.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Materials

Conventional thermosetting powder coatings are classified into five major curing systems: epoxy, epoxy/polyester, polyester, polyurethane and acrylic^{12,13,14}. In this study, low temperature curing (120°C) epoxy/polyester powder coating was used. It was purchased from LIFCO industry, and was essentially constituted by a mixture of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), carboxyl polyester

resins, mineral fillers and other additives. The composite substrate is a modified epoxy matrix prepreg containing epoxy and sulfone functional groups with glass and carbon fibers. It has been produced by laying up pre-impregnated (prepreg) laminates followed by a curing treatment. These prepregs were manufactured by HEXCEL composite and designed for a curing program at 180°C.

2.2 Sample and cross section preparation

In order to prepare the coated-composite plates, an in-mold powder coating process has been performed (Figure 1). Firstly, release agent is applied on the mold. The epoxy/polyester powder coating was sprayed by electrostatic gun onto a conductive mold then heated for different time/temperature conditions. At this stage, the powders flow and coalesce to form a partially crosslinked films. Next, the sheets of prepreg composite materials were laid up on pre-heated powder layer, and the in-mold coating composite samples were fully cured and chemically bonded with a curing cycle (2h at 120°C and 2h at 180°C)^{14,15}. In order to study the effect of conversion degree of powder coating on the interface properties, different samples have been prepared by varying, in the first stage, (i) the pre-heating times of the powder coating in the mold (15 min, 20 min, 40 min, 60 min) and/or (ii) the curing temperature (120°C and 160°C). Cross sections were prepared by cutting the coated composite plate, then wrapped by acrylic resin and polished as smooth as possible.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram illustrating the general process of in-mold powder coatings.

2.3 Characterization techniques

2.3.1 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Samples were analyzed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) coupled with Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector. SEM-EDX was used for studying the microstructure and the elemental composition of the interface. Experiments were carried out on a Zeiss Supra 40 VP microscope equipped with energy dispersive X-ray analyzer. Samples were coated with thin layer of carbon by discharge method then were scanned in backscattered electrons (BSE) with acceleration voltage of 10-20 keV on the polished edge of the sample.

2.3.2 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy measurements (FTIR)

Attenuated Total Reflectance Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-IR) has been used to chemically characterize the coating/composite samples. IR analysis in depth has been performed by removing the coating, layer by layer, to reach the composite material (as schematized in Figure 2). The erosion has been controlled by using a micrometric gauge, and the measurements were carried out every 2-10 μm on three different regions. The ATR mode allowed us to analyze the first microns from the surface. Measurements were done using a Thermo-Nicolet Nexus FTIR equipped with an ATR accessory. All spectra were recorded with 64 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

Figure 2 : Schematic representation illustrating the successive ATR-FTIR analysis in the depth of the coating.

2.3.4 Modulated Temperature Differential Scanning Calorimetry (MTDSC)

MTDSC experiments were performed using a TA Instrument DSC Q100. The scans were carried out under a nitrogen purge, and the samples (about 5 mg) were placed in holed aluminum pans. An empty pan was used as the reference. In order to determine the glass transition temperatures, samples were heated from 40°C to 260°C with a scanning rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The midpoint temperature of the C_p jump was taken as glass transition temperature (T_g).

Samples for MTDSC experiments were prepared by using a microtome (Leica Microsystems). The sections were cut parallel to the interface (Figure 3). The thicknesses of the sections were about $40\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 3 : Schematic of the sample preparation for MTDSC analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Structural characterization of the interface-interphase

Figure 4 shows SEM cross section micrographs taken for four coated composite plates prepared with different conditions. Before application of the composite prepregs in the mold, the degrees of conversion of the epoxy/polyester powder coating were different. These degrees were calculated from DSC measurements and reported in the Table 1. The micrograph (A), which corresponds to the sample where the degree of conversion was 48%, showed micrometric nodules (droplets) within the coating. The size of these nodules is widely variable and ranged from few micrometers to about $50\ \mu\text{m}$. This result suggests a diffusion process from the composite material to the powder coating during the curing program. Because the powder coating was not completely crosslinked, the migration of nodules across the interface can be occurred. In consequence, the interface between the composite and the coating

has been disappeared, and an organic/organic heterogeneous interphase has been created.

Condition	Conversion degree ($\pm 5\%$)
20 min, 120°C	48%
40 min, 120°C	69%
60 min, 120°C	92%
15 min, 160°C	67%

Table 1 : Values of the conversion degree of powder coating as determined from DSC analysis.

On one hand, elemental EDX analysis shows the presence of carbon, sulfur, oxygen, titanium and other minor elements. A high signal corresponding to titanium element appears onto coating matrix, suggesting a high amount of TiO_2 mineral filler. Interestingly, sulfur element has been only detected onto nodules and composite substrate (Figure 5). One can note that the epoxy composite contains polyethersulfone (PES), which could be constituted the only source of sulfur element.

On the other hand, the micrographs (B, C and D) in Figure 4, which correspond to the samples with conversion degrees from 67% to 92%, displayed clear interfaces between the coatings and the substrates. Here, the high crosslinked matrix prevented the penetration of nodules previously observed at relative low conversion degree (48%). The interface/interphase observed in the different cases was responsible for adhesion mechanisms. Its physicochemical properties constitute a key element to understand such mechanisms, as we well present in the next sections.

Figure 4. Cross section SEM micrographs showing the structural properties of the interface/interphase between the coating and the substrate. The powder coating was pre-heated at 120°C for 20 min (A), 40 min (B), 60 min (C), and at 160°C for 15 min (D).

Figure 5. SEM micrograph showing the nodules into paint matrix (a) and corresponding EDX mapping of sulfur (b) and titanium (c).

3.2 Chemical characterization by FTIR spectroscopy

The chemical features of the crosslinked powder coating and composite material were firstly studied by FTIR spectroscopy in ATR mode. Figure 6 shows the obtained spectra in the range of 800-1800 cm^{-1} . Table 2 indicates the significant vibration frequencies related to the functional groups of each compound. Infrared spectroscopy reveals some important differences between the epoxy/polyester powder coating and the epoxy-based composite. These differences will be helpful for choosing the significant IR peaks, which could be easily analyzed.

Figure 6 : FTIR spectra of crosslinked powder coating (a) and composite substrate (b) in the range of 800-1800 cm^{-1} .

Position (cm^{-1})	Peak assignment
1034, 1070, 1148	$\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{O}=\text{S}=\text{O})$
1576	Vibration of (C=C) aromatic
1714	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$

Table 2 : Significant IR peaks of crosslinked powder coating and composite substrate.¹⁶

The IR spectrum of the powder coating (Figure 6.a) shows an intense peak at 1714 cm^{-1} which is associated to the C=O stretching vibration of polyester group. This peak is not present in the IR spectrum of composite. Figure 6.b, corresponding to IR spectrum of composite, reveals three significant peaks at 1034, 1070 and 1148 cm^{-1} which are attributed to stretching vibration of sulfoxide and sulfone groups. A common peak at 1576 cm^{-1} present in powder coating and composite matrix was observed and assigned to the aromatic rings. The peaks at 1714 cm^{-1} and 1148 cm^{-1} constitute good signatures of the powder coating and composite respectively. In order to study the chemical composition across the coating/composite interface, we have determined the integrated areas of the selected peaks as a function of the penetration depths in the coating (Figure 7). Note that we have realized the IR spectra step by step by removing the coating, layer by layer, from the top surface of the coating to the composite substrate (see Figure 2).

As shown in Figure 7, the intensities of the selected IR peaks vary across the coating/composite interface. On one hand, when the powder coating was pre-cured for 20 min at 120°C, the intensity of the C=O peak at 1714 cm^{-1} gradually decreased from the coating to the substrate side (Figure 7.a). Coating signal becomes very low after erosion of $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, the intensity of the peak at 1148 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the composite substrate, increased to reach a first maximum at about 60 μm of penetration. Then, a high variation has been observed due to the presence of glass fibers inside the composite. The analysis of the aromatic peak at 1576 cm^{-1} showed the same variation observed for sulfone peak (composite). In all the cases, the intensities of C=C aromatic peak are higher than those of sulfone groups (Figure 7.a). This difference is due to the contribution of the C=C aromatic groups of the coating in the calculated intensity.

Figure 7 : Evolution of the intensities of significant IR peaks across the coating/composite interface (♦ Carbonyl group,▲ Sulfone group, ■ aromatic ring). The powder coating was pre-heated at 120°C for 20 min (a), 40 min (b), 60 min (c), and at 160°C for 15 min (d).

When the powder coating was pre-cured for 40 min or 60 min at 120°C (Figure 7.b and 7.c), the variations of the IR peak intensities were very different from that of 20 min at 120°C. The intensity of the C=O peak at 1714 cm^{-1} remains unchanged over the entire coating thickness. After removing of $\sim 90 \mu\text{m}$ of coating, a sharp decrease in intensity was observed. On the contrary, the peak at 1148 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the composite signal, showed a high increase. The same result has been obtained when the powder coating was pre-cured for 15 min at 160°C (Figure 7.d).

Based on this data, FTIR analysis showed the formation of a large heterogeneous interphase (around 150 μm) when the powder coating has a low conversion degree ($\sim 48\%$ obtained by pre-heating for 20 min at 120°C). The interphase disappeared when the conversion degree was higher than $\sim 65\%$.

The formation of heterogeneous interphase depends on the pre-curing conditions of the powder coating.

3.2 Thermal properties of the interface-interphase coating/composite

MTDSC experiments were firstly performed on film coating and non-coated substrate. The glass transition temperatures (T_g) were about 82°C and 200°C for free film coating and pure substrate, respectively (Figure 8.a). No significant difference between the types of coating (20min/120°C and 60min/120°C) has been observed. This can be explained by the fact that the two samples were also cured for a supplementary heating cycle (2h at 120°C + 2h at 180°C). Therefore, the two paint matrices were fully crosslinked and similar results were obtained by thermal analysis.

Figure 7: (a) MTDSC thermograms of crosslinked powder coatings film and pure composite substrate. (b) and (c) MTDSC thermograms obtained for two different coated substrates. The powder coating was pre-cured for 20 min at 120°C (b) and for 60 min at 120°C (c).

MTDSC results obtained from the top surface to the bulk of the sample are illustrated in Figure 7.b and 7.c. For the first sample, where the powder coating was pre-cured for 20 min at 120°C, the glass transition $T_g(\text{coating})$ appeared at about 82°C. When approaching to the interface region (section 2, 3 and 4), thermal analysis showed a gradual decrease in T_g signal (Figure 7.b). In parallel, two T_g signals appeared at about 200°C and 225°C: the first one corresponds to the glass transition of composite material and the second one can be attributed to the polyethersulfone (PES) nodules observed within the heterogeneous interphase (see Figure 4.a). We note that PES (thermoplastic toughening) has been widely used in aerospace and automotive industries because it enhances toughness without compromising other desirable properties of composite materials^{17,18}. The phase separation of thermoplastic-modified epoxy systems was already reported in the literature^{19,20,21,22}. In this study, due to the contact of the coating with modified epoxy system, the phase separation induced the formation of heterogeneous interphase within the coating matrix.

When the powder coating was pre-cured for 60 min at 120°C (Figure 7.c), the thermal analysis, done on section 1 and 2 logically showed the glass transition of coating (82°C). Approaching the interface, one glass transition T_g corresponding to the composite substrate has been observed at 200°C. However, no T_g at 225°C has been detected, indicating the absence of the interphase found in the first case. Note here that similar results have been obtained for the thermal analysis of the samples pre-cured for 40 min at 120°C and 15 min at 160°C.

4 Conclusion

In the present work, a combination of different tests was envisaged in order to study the influence of powder coating pre-curing time on interface coating/epoxy matrix composite. Good correlations have been obtained between the structural, thermal and chemical analysis. The pre-curing time of powder coating, and consequently the degree of conversion, has a clear effect on the formation of interphase/interface between coating and composite substrate. The in-mold powder coating method was an efficiency way for painting epoxy based

composites. In relation, this study looks promising for further investigation concerning the influence of hydrothermal ageing on physicochemical properties of such systems.

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